

Time Reversal and Wavefunction*(x,t) Wavefunction(x,t)?

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In a previous note (1) we argued that the free particle classical action A (relativistic or nonrelativistic) may be written in terms of $v=x/t$ and then varied in x and t independently. One finds that $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ implying $A = -Et + px$ with x and t independent. This is the opposite of the classical mechanical idea of $x(t)$. Creating an eigenvalue equation yields $-id/dx \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $id/dt \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$. $\exp(iA)$ plays the role of an unusual type of probability we argue which describes two dimensional periodicity ($\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$). We have argued that the quantum particle is the medium for a two dimensional wavelike motion of an energy-momentum wave. A wave type structure is needed to describe dynamics (like a classical wave), but unlike a classical wave two dimensions are required because there is no preference of any x point for a free particle. Both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ both treat x in a preferential manner as their values vary with x . For a classical wave this is fine because the creation point of the wave imposes boundary conditions, but there is no such boundary condition imposed on a free particle. $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ must somehow then link to $P(x) = \text{constant}$.

One may note that $\exp(-iA)\exp(iA) = 1$ for the free particle. This may be argued to be linked to spatial invariance i.e. $P(x) = \text{constant}$ where $P(x)$ is not $\exp(ipx)$. Here we argue that $\exp(-iA)\exp(iA)$ represents a product of two unusual probabilities, one for motion in a certain direction and the other for the time reversed scenario. If the quantum particle is the medium of an energy-momentum wave $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$, then the product of the regular and time reversed unusual probabilities cancel or undo each other. In other words one does not see any change in space as long as one has a noninteracting $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. Given that $-id/dx$ is a linear operator this product yields a momentum of 0.

We consider this idea and its implications on a momentum distribution $\sum \text{ over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which may represent a bound state or other states. In particular, it seems that $P(x) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ which yields a classical type of probability ($P(x)$ real, positive and normalized to 1) is linked to a product (merging) of forward and time reversed situations so that any spatial density which remain due to the quantum particle acting as a medium for an energy-momentum wave (as well as the time reversed part) would represent an actual change in spatial density. $\exp(ipx)$ already contains two periodic spatial functions ($\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$), but does not manifest it unless there is an interaction.

Classical Action and Quantum Free Particle

A classical free particle moves with velocity $v=x/t = \text{constant}$. Taking the relativistic $A = \text{free particle classical action} = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv}$ or nonrelativistic $A = t \cdot \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ and writes $v=x/t$ and varying x and t independently, one obtains:

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A = p \text{ ((1a)) and } d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E \text{ ((1b))}$$

This breaks with the classical mechanical idea of $x(t)$. ((1a)) and ((1b)) seem to be focused solely on energy and energy flow, not the motion of the particle. From ((1)):

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } t \text{ and } x \text{ are independent}$$

Creating eigenvalue equations yields: $-i\partial/\partial x \text{ partial exp}(iA) = p \text{ exp}(iA) \quad ((3a))$ and

$$i\partial/\partial t \text{ partial exp}(iA) = E \text{ exp}(iA) \quad ((3b))$$

One may consider $\text{exp}(iA)$ represents a kind of unusual dynamical probability associated with energy and momentum flow. We argue that this motion is linked to $dA = 0 = -dE t + dp x$ or $x/t = dp/dE = v = p/E$ for a free relativistic particle. Thus, the two dimensional wave type object $\text{exp}(-iEt+ipx)$ seems to be linked to the same velocity as a classical free particle. Such a particle should not have any probability as a function of x , but $\text{exp}(ipx-iEt)$ is a function of this variable. One may note that a classical wave takes the form $\cos(px-Et)$, but with a different velocity namely $v_{\text{wave}} = E/p$. Nevertheless a classical wave involves conserved changes in the medium in a periodic manner. For example, a sound wave involves a high density region with a lower density one before it. This pattern is repeated in time.

If one considers $dA=0$ as depending on dE and dp , one focuses on an energy-momentum disturbance which is like a classical particle. Like the classical wave, one might argue that the energy-momentum wave uses the quantum single free particle as a medium, but two dimensions $\text{exp}(ipx)$ and not one like the classical wave (sound, water wave) are involved. This is necessary so that there is no preference given to any x . For the classical wave $\cos(-wt+px)$ is based on a boundary condition at the point at which the wave is created and so the bias is allowed. A particle moving with constant v cannot have any preference for any x value, but $\text{exp}(ipx)$ does and so must be mapped into a unbiased form i.e $P(x)=\text{constant}$.

Given that $-i\partial/\partial x$ is a linear operator in ((3a)) $\text{exp}(-ipx)\text{exp}(ipx) = 1$ and has a momentum of 0. Using the full probability $\text{exp}(-iEt+ipx)$ shows that $(\text{exp}(-iEt+ipx))^* \text{exp}(-iEt+ipx)$ where $*$ denotes the complex conjugate undoes the energy-momentum wave i.e. one has an AND situation of the unusual probabilities $\text{exp}(-iEt+ipx)$ and its time-reversed form. This creates the link with $v=x/t = \text{constant}$ which implies that there should be a connection with the classical mechanical particle and introduces a new probability $P(x) = (\text{unusual probability})^* (\text{unusual probability})$. $\text{exp}(ipx)$ contains two periodic functions which are nonlocal in x . We have argued that these are due to the quantum particle acting as the medium for an energy-momentum wave. In other words there is physical behaviour involved which should manifest itself, although it does not appear to visibly do so as a quantum free particle moves along hence $P(x)=\text{constant}$. Thinking of a quantum particle moving along, however, makes use of the idea $x(t)$ which does not apply in a quantum picture. $\text{exp}(ipx)$ represents a kind of probability linked to energy flow (momentum) p in a certain direction, but as a probability it applies to all x points. It is almost like a steady flow picture. If the particle may follow different paths (e.g. a two slit scenario) one may add the unusual probabilities for each path to obtain an overall result which involves interference of the unusual probabilities i.e. accounts for their dynamical nonlocal probabilities. Thus there is a definite physical aspect to the periodicities in $\text{exp}(ipx)$. (Ultimately one takes $(\text{exp}(ip x_1) + \text{exp}(ip x_2))$ and multiplies by the complex conjugate to get a classical type of

probability, but the result is already determined by the added unusual probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx1)$.

This leads to the question: Why should one use $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ to create a measurable probability if one already has the unusual probability (amplitude) $\exp(ipx)$.

$\exp(-ipx + iEt)\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ versus $(\exp(-ipx) + \exp(ipx))\exp(iEt)$

In the last section we argued that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ represents a dynamical type of probability with x and t independent. It is closely linked to the classical wave solution $\cos(-wt+kx)$ except that it is two dimensional. We thus argue that dynamically there is a removal of probability linked to an increase in probability of the single particle medium, but that this occurs in two dimensions because for a free particle one does not have any preference in space. A classical wave is different. It must be created in a medium at an x point and a time t . Thus one follows $x(t)$. For example, a surface water wave may be created by dropping an object in water. At this point there is a particular perturbation of the water which governs initial crest and trough positions. For a particle with momentum p , there can be no x preference. One has no idea where (which x) it was created. Various boundary conditions, however, in space may bias one "x" path versus another i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ may develop phase shifts as in the two-slit scenario.

A dynamical wave (either classical or the quantum $\exp(ipx)$ two wave has negative and positive regions. From the point of view of a quantum measurement, however, these seem the same. A very hand wavy analogy is that a boat on a smooth surface interacts with both the crest and trough of a wave. Although one is above the smooth level and the other below, both create similar disturbances compared with smooth sailing. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ which contains two waves each with positive and negative regions should link to a constant $P(x)$ which occurs if one takes the product $\exp(iEt-ipx)\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ i.e. tries to create and undo a probability wave. Undoing a probability wave occurs by taking the complex conjugate which we argue is like considering a time reversed process.

This begs the question: How does one describe $\exp(-iEt) (\exp(-ipx) + \exp(ipx))$? In this case, one has both forward flow p and backward $-p$. There is no $x(t)$ in this picture so each point x is an average of the dynamics of the forward and backward motion. Thus interference may occur so that the sum describes a very different situation from that of a free particle. One cannot think of this sum as representing a particle moving in one direction during one time interval and then hitting a wall and moving in the opposite direction during another time interval. That is an $x(t)$ picture and $A = -Et+px$ is an approach which treats x and t as independent. Nevertheless even in the quantum picture $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ for the same particle do not arise out of nowhere. There must be a barrier (e.g. square well potential as an example) which leads to the two coexisting. This barrier represents a boundary condition mathematically and physically affects the dynamics of $\exp(ipx)$ at this boundary (much like dropping a rock at point x in water imposes initial crest trough positioning). $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ do not undo each other like in the product they only eliminate some of the dynamics. This dynamics, however, is what kept $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ linked to a $P(x)=\text{constant}$ of x . Disrupting it may lead to a $P(x)$ not equal to a constant. In fact, the sum leads to a real solution $2 \cos(px)$, but this still describes dynamics with positive and negative values. As a result, one needs to consider undoing the entire result i.e.

$\exp(iEt) 2\cos(px) \exp(-iEt) 2\cos(px) = 4 \cos(px)\cos(px)$ unnormalized.

$W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ as a New Probability

If the dynamics of a quantum particle acting as a medium for an energy-momentum wave are described by $\exp(ipx)$ as an unusual probability, why would one wish to go beyond this? For example, for the case of a bound state, one may create an ensemble using $W(x)=\sum$ over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and write a conservation of energy equation:

$$\left\{ \sum \text{over } p \quad a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

Boundary conditions causing $W(x)$ to drop at high and low x values may be imposed. The first term in ((4)) may be written as: $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ and one may create a differential equation which may be solved for $W(x)$. Noting that $\exp(-iEt)$ applied to a free particle and that one now has a resonance type of energy for the ensemble $W(x)$ one may consider:

$$\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx) \text{ becoming } \exp(-iEnt) W(x) \quad ((5))$$

((4)) deals with the behaviour of an ensemble. Each member $\exp(ipx)$ describes a quantum particle acting as the medium for an energy-momentum wave i.e a probabilistic type of object. This allows one to find resonance energies E_n such that each $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to the same $\exp(-iEnt)$. As seen with the two slit situation, probabilistic waves may interfere and lead to physically detectable density/intensity patterns. In other words the periodicity of $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ is physical. It was seen, however, that it manifests itself when one creates “sums” of $\exp(ipx)$'s. The pattern itself should be described by $P(x)$ where this probability is real and positive and normalized to 1. This is not at all the same as the unusual probability $\exp(ipx)$. The question becomes: How should one obtain $P(x)$?

In an earlier section we noted that $(\exp(iEt-ipx)) \exp(-iEt+ipx) = 1$ and describes momentum 0. It also represents an unusual probability multiplied by its complex conjugate which we argue is a time reversed situation. Even though $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ is periodic and this periodicity is physically real, if one can take the time reversed unusual probability and multiply it by its complex conjugate one may cause the periodicity to locally disappear (i.e. at each x). This, however, does not happen if one has a sum of $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities with different p 's. Then locally (at x) one may see $\exp(i(p_1-p_2)x)$ type terms. Ultimately one should have real number (object * object = real), but the periodicity will remain locally. In other words the scenario and its complex conjugate i.e. time reversed scenario taken as an AND probability are unable to erase the density change. Given that the approach introduced in the first section does not depend on $x(t)$, but on a probability profile in space (and time), this density should be measurable (for repeated measurements of a bound state or a single measurement on each member of an ensemble of bound states.)

For a bound state one has $\exp(-iEnt) W_n(x)$ and so even though $W_n(x)$ is real and the complex conjugate does not apply to it, it does apply to $\exp(-iEnt)$ and one may consider:

$$W_n(x)W_n(x) = P(x) \text{ for a bound state } W_n(x) \quad ((5))$$

One may examine the bound state in more detail. For a $W_n(x)$ from an oscillator for example, $W_n(x)$ is a real periodic function i.e. has positive and negative values. Thus $W_n(x)$ still has unusual probabilistic features which means that the particle is now the medium of a resonance different from that of $\exp(ipx)$. Only one dimension appears (due to combined forward and backward motions in an OR situation i.e. $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ for $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p)=-a(-p)$), but there is still the localized hump trough pattern analogous to the response to a classical wave. Given that one has a single particle and not many particles, this is interpreted as being linked to losing probability in one region (the negative region) and gaining it in another such that on average one has zero. This periodicity remains in $W_n(x)W_n(x)$, but $\exp(iEnt)$ $\exp(-iEnt)$ becomes 1. The fact that the crest is positive in a certain x range and negative for the trough (i.e. a different x region) is not an issue because both $W_n(x)$ and $-W_n(x)$ are solutions of the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Orthogonality

One may note that $W^*(x)W(x)$ contains terms such as $a(p_1)^*\exp(-ip_1x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ which contain $\exp(i(-p_1+p_2)x)$. In other words one has an overall result which is of the form of a single free particle unusual probability. Combining these two probabilities as an AND situation leads to an overall local result which looks like a single amplitude i.e. has periodic spatial values. These are then local density changes which do not disappear.

A question one may ask is: What happens over all of space? For each component, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ one has a crest and a trough which cancel each other (just as in a classical wave) due to conservation of the medium. Here one has a single particle as a medium and deals with probabilities. Thus cross terms such as: $a(p_1)^*\exp(-ip_1x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ integrate to 0 i.e. are orthogonal.

One may consider: $\int W^*(x) a(p)\exp(ipx) dx = a^*(p)a(p) \quad ((6))$. In such a case one is considering an AND probability situation (using amplitudes) of a single free particle momentum with the time reversed entire $W(x)$. One integrates over all of space so one knows $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$, but has no information about position.

Another example is:

$$W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \ a(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) \ W_n(x) \quad ((6))$$

It is interesting to note that not only are $W_n(x)$ orthonormal in x space, but $\exp(-iE_n t)$'s are orthogonal in t space. Here t and x are decoupled. One may take $\int dt \ W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ and find a time independent density in space = $\text{Sum over } n \ W_n(x)W_n(x) \ a_n^*(E_n)a_n(E_n)$

Time Reversed Situation Mixed with Regular Situation

If one considers only dynamics e.g. $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle or $W(x,t)$ for a more general situation, the idea of a time reversed wavefunction $W^*(x,t)$ does not appear. It is only if one wishes to create classical-like probabilities $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ or $P(p)= a^*(p)a(p)$ (e.g. for a bound

state) which describe experimental measurables that one is forced to introduce the time-reversed unusual probability (i.e. the wavefunction) in an AND situation with its non-time-reversed probability to see if spatial non-locality due to the response of an energy-momentum wave (which creates the form $\exp(ipx)$ to describe the single particle) disappear or not. For a single $\exp(ipx)$ they do, but for sums one sees local interference.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ represents a kind of unusual probability which describes the dynamics of an energy-momentum wave for which a single particle is the medium and velocity is $dp/dE = p/E = v$ for a relativistic particle. One has two waves ($\cos(px-Et)$, $\sin(px-Et)$) because even though each behaves as a classical wave (although the two are phase shifted) one cannot have any preference in x space. A classical wave has a preference in x space i.e. a crest occurs in one x region and the trough in another because there is a boundary condition at the point at which it is created. A particle with constant p has no such boundary condition. It must be linked to invariance in space, yet $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ shows x and t dependent variations.

We suggest that to eliminate these, one may multiply this unusual probability by its time reversed state i.e. its complex conjugate. An AND probability describes an undoing of the wave. What is the situation of an OR probability? This seems to suggest some kind of imposed boundary conditions due to a potential and leads to $[\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)]\exp(-iEt)$. This is a different situation because one may have space preference and interference of dynamical behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. The sum yields $2\cos(px)$ which gives preference to different x points. Even if one multiplies by the complex conjugate (the time reversed state) this preference is not erased because it arises due to the physical presence of boundary conditions i.e. the walls of a square well potential. If one did not have these boundaries i.e. the square well potential one would have either a free $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ or a free $\exp(-iEt-ipx)$, but not a sum for the same single quantum particle.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)